

Community Detection for Primary Care Service Areas in Chile: Balancing Granularity and Flow Localisation

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Summary

This study evaluated three community detection algorithms to delineate Primary Care Service Areas (PCSAs) in Chile. While prior applications have focused on hospital settings, often creating large multi-centre areas, there is a need for methods tailored to Primary Care, balancing single-centre areas with strong local flows. Using anonymised, geocoded patient-level data from a Chilean Health Service, networks of healthcare-seeking flows were analysed under different edge-weighting schemes, spatial aggregations, and post-processing refinements. Infomap outperformed modularity-based methods (Louvain and Leiden), generating more granular PCSAs with strong within-area flows. These findings guide algorithm choice for meaningful PCSAs and planning equitable access.

KEYWORDS: Primary Care Service Areas, Community Detection Algorithms, Healthcare Planning, Chile

1 Introduction

In Chile, primary healthcare (PHC) allows individuals to register at and access any centre regardless of residence (Gattini Collao, 2019). While this policy promotes choice, it creates tensions between individual autonomy and system planning. Behaviourally informed Primary Care Service Areas (PCSAs) help address this gap by defining service areas from observed utilisation patterns, rather than administrative boundaries, supporting more efficient primary care planning (Goodman et al., 2003).

Network-based community detection algorithms are increasingly used to delineate service areas by grouping geographic units according to shared patient flows. In hospital-based studies, these

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algorithms often produced highly localised, multi-centre service areas that reflect shared demand across facilities (Hu et al., 2018; Pinheiro et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021). While effective for capturing flows, PHC systems like Chile’s require each centre to serve a defined local population (Gattini Collao, 2019), making single-centre service areas the ideal outcome.

In this context, this study compares three community detection algorithms in their ability to generate granular PCSAs that balance behavioural coherence with institutional requirements. It evaluates their capacity to produce predominantly single-centre service areas while maximising internal consultation flows, and assesses how spatial aggregation, edge weighting, and post-processing shape this balance. The optimal configuration is then applied in a case study to highlight inequities in public and private PHC access.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Study Area and Datasets

The study focuses on the South-Eastern sector of Chile’s Metropolitan Region, encompassing seven municipalities under the Servicio de Salud Metropolitano Sur Oriente (SSMSO, Figure 1). Patient-level consultation data for 2023 were obtained from SSMSO with ethical approval, including registered and visited PHC centres, commune of residence, sex, age group, and location, supplemented with private healthcare visits through Chile’s Free Choice Scheme.

PHC centre locations were sourced from the Department of Health Statistics and Information (DEIS, 2025) (43 centres), and spatial units from the National Institute of Statistics (INE, 2025), combining 2023 Pre-Census urban units, 2017 rural units, and commune boundaries. Socioeconomic stratification was derived from the Socio-Material and Territorial Index (ISMT) (OCUC, 2022) based on 2017 census data, allowing population counts to be split into low, middle, and high socioeconomic groups.

1. La Florida 2. La Pintana 3. La Granja 4. Pirque 5. Puente Alto 6. San José de Maipo 7. San Ramón

Figure 1: Study area

2.2 PCSA Delineation Workflow

A four-stage workflow was implemented (Figure 2). First, Voronoi diagrams were generated from the original census units, which were not spatially contiguous in urban areas, and geocoded patient data were linked to estimate total population. ISMT estimates were then used to disaggregate populations into three socioeconomic groups (Figure 2A).

Figure 2: PCSA Delineation Workflow: A) Stage 1: Data preparation, B) Stage 2: Multi-Scale Regionalisation Process, C) Stage 3: Community Detection, and D) Stage 4: Model Assessment.

Next, the Voronoi polygons, which contained on average 106 registered patients, were aggregated into larger “tracts” using AZTool (Cockings et al., 2011). Fourteen tract configurations were produced, targeting populations from 200 to 1,500, with aggregation guided by socioeconomic population counts and spatial compactness (Figure 2B).

In Stage 3 (Figure 2C), consultation flows were aggregated into tracts to build networks linking residential areas to PHC centres. Following Hu et al. (2018), nodes were tract centroids weighted by population, and edges represented patient visits. Three community detection algorithms were applied: Louvain and Leiden (modularity maximisation) and Infomap (codelength minimisation). At the finest spatial scale, Infomap initially produced 27 communities, which served as a baseline. The modularity based algorithms were adjusted to match this baseline and then iteratively tuned to approximate the number of health centres.

Because these algorithms do not enforce spatial contiguity, two post-processing strategies reassigned disconnected tracts: one adapted from Wang et al. (2021), minimising changes to modularity or codelength, and one assigning tracts to the neighbouring community with the strongest connection. Configurations are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Configuration Settings for Community Detection

Setting	Description	Values Used / Range
Trials	Number of repeated runs conducted for each algorithm (excluding Louvain)	30
Refinement strategy	Spatial enforcement strategies applied after community-detection results	None; Minimum impact score; Strongest connection
Spatial scale	Target average population per tract for aggregation	200 to 1500 (increments of 100)
Edge weight	Network edge weighting strategies used during graph construction	Total visits; Visit share; Combined score
Number of modules	Parameter enforcing a specific number of communities (Infomap only)	27 to 43 (step = 1)
Resolution	Resolution parameter for modularity-based algorithms (Louvain, Leiden)	3.5 to 13.5 (step = 0.1)

Performance was assessed using the number of communities with internal consultation flows and the Localisation Index (LI), indicating the proportion of care used within PCSA boundaries (Goodman et al., 2003).

Finally, the best-performing PCSA configuration was used to assess healthcare access. Age- and sex-standardised Relative Access Ratios (SRARs) for public, private, and combined services were computed relative to overall study-area access, with values above 1 indicating higher-than-expected access. PCSAs were classified accordingly (Table 2), and considered compensated when reduced access in one sector was offset by higher access in the other (combined SRAR > 1).

Table 2: Healthcare Access Categories Based on SRAR Thresholds

SRAR in Public Services	SRAR in Private Services	SRAR Combined	Category
>1	>1	>1	Equitable Access
>1	<1	>1	Compensated through Public Access
>1	<1	<1	Insufficient Public Compensation
<1	>1	>1	Compensated through Private Access
<1	>1	<1	Insufficient Private Compensation
<1	<1	<1	Limited Access

3 Results

Across 27,972 solutions, Infomap consistently produced the most suitable PCSA delineations. The optimal configuration—tracts averaging 300 patients with visit-share weighting—yielded a mean LI of 0.68 and 39 PCSAs, closely aligning with individual centres while preserving strong internal flows (Figure 3). Infomap maintained stable performance across scales and weighting schemes (LI between 0.60 and 0.70), whereas Louvain and Leiden generated fewer meaningful communities, with LI values declining sharply beyond 31 PCSAs (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Number of communities with internal flows and the mean of the mean Localisation Index (LI) for the best algorithm outcomes across spatial scales (Target Population) and edge weighting schemes. Results correspond to models without spatial enforcement strategies.

Edge weighting also shaped delineation quality. For Infomap, visit-share and combined weighting outperformed raw visit counts, while weighting had minor effects on Louvain and Leiden. Post-processing strategies produced similar LI values, but assigning tracts to the strongest-connected community was far more efficient, reducing Infomap’s runtime fivefold (Table 3).

Figure 4: Relationship between the number of communities with internal flows and the Localisation Index across all model outcomes without spatial enforcement strategies

Table 3: Comparison of spatial enforcement strategies across all model outcomes. Standard deviations are shown in parentheses.

Algorithm	Average Execution Time (seconds)		Average Mean LI	
	Min. Impact Score	Strongest Connection	Min. Impact Score	Strongest Connection
Infomap	5.564 (6.044)	1.028 (0.496)	0.701 (0.026)	0.703 (0.026)
Leiden	1.646 (1.721)	1.062 (0.602)	0.701 (0.030)	0.700 (0.032)
Louvain	1.233 (0.957)	0.926 (0.467)	0.702 (0.025)	0.702 (0.025)

In the case study, access patterns varied substantially across PCSAs (Figure 5). About 36% of PCSAs had limited access to private services, offset by higher-than-expected public access. Areas with lower-than-expected public access without private compensation were concentrated in Puente Alto, while PCSAs where private services compensated for low public access occurred only in La Florida. PCSAs facing universally limited access—both public and private below expected levels—were mainly in Puente Alto and La Granja. Equitable access ($SRAR > 1$ for both sectors) was rare, observed in only three PCSAs, two in Pirque.

Figure 5: Spatial Distribution of Healthcare Access Categories at PCSA level.

4 Conclusions

This study introduces a methodology for delineating PCSAs using geocoded patient data and community-detection algorithms. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, it is the first comparative application of these three algorithms in a PHC context. Network construction choices—particularly spatial aggregation and edge weighting—along with algorithm selection, critically shape PCSA granularity and functional quality. Infomap was most effective in generating fine-grained, single-centre service areas while preserving internal consultation flows.

Limitations include lower geocoding completeness in rural areas, missing patient flows beyond the study boundary, and restriction to a single year of data. Despite these constraints, the methodology provides a robust foundation for generating meaningful PCSAs. Future work could explore additional community detection algorithms and broader geographic coverage to assess whether Infomap continues to offer the best balance between spatial granularity and flow localisation.

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6 Biography

Felipe Portales holds an MSc in GIS and has a professional background in public health and health services in Chile. His research interests include health geography, quantitative methods, and the development of open-source spatial analysis workflows and bespoke web-mapping solutions.

Zhiqiang Feng is a senior lecturer in GIS and human geography at the School of Geosciences of University of Edinburgh. His research interests are health geography, GIS, spatial analysis, population geography and longitudinal data analysis.

Francisco Suárez is an IT professional with training in business intelligence, data mining, and big data. He has experience designing, implementing, and using health information systems to support decision-making. His research focuses on generating knowledge for health event anticipation, with territorial and life-course analysis to improve care processes.

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